

Varying Valency of Platinum with Respect to Mercaptanic Radicles. Part VII.

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Many complex compounds derived from chloroplatinic acid and various organic thio-compounds (mercaptans, sulphides, disulphides etc.) have already been described (Rây, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 872; Rây, *ibid.*, 1922, 121, 1283; Rây, *ibid.*, 1923, 123, 133; Rây and Bose-Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 178). The action of various bases on some of these complex bodies to elucidate their constitutions has also been investigated (Rây, Guha and Bose-Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 155; Rây, Guha and Bose-Rây, *ibid.*, 1926, 3, 358; Rây, Bose-Rây and Adhikari, *ibid.*, 1927, 4, 467).

In the present work, the action of another organic thio-compound, benzyl sulphide, on chloroplatinic acid has been studied and the compounds (1) $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}^*$ and (2) $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ (also a molecular compound of the above two, $\text{Pt}_2\text{Cl}_6 \cdot 4\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$) have been obtained.

These two compounds have then been subjected to the action of bases like ammonia, pyridine, etc., and a study of the resulting products has been found to throw considerable light on the constitution of the parent bodies (*cf.* Rây, Guha and Bose-Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 155; Rây, Bose-Rây and Adhikari, *ibid.*, 1927, 3, 467). The products are mostly compounds of the Werner type, which directly suggests that the compounds (1) and (2) themselves possess Werner constitutions.

Constitution of $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$.

Molecular weight determination in naphthalene by the freezing-point method corresponds to the single formula. Hence it cannot be a molecular compound of $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ (*cf.* the formula of $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$: Rây and Bose-Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 178; Rây, Guha and Bose-Rây, *ibid.*, 1926, 3, 155) or possess the formula $[\text{Pt}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})_4] \cdot \text{PtCl}_6$ (*cf.* the formula for $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ suggested by (Tschugaeff, *Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1913, 82, 420). That

* In this paper the benzyl radical, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2$, will be written as Bz.

it is not a molecular compound of $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ is further proved by the fact that it could not be broken up on crystallisation from any of the solvents like benzene, chloroform, naphthalene—in which the substance was soluble—and also by the fact that by the action of bases, it has not yet given any compound of the type $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot n\text{B}$ (when B=bases) (*vide infra*), which would have been expected had $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ been one of its components. These properties of the compound may be contrasted with a true molecular compound, $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, whose constitution has been discussed by Rāy and Bose-Rāy and by Rāy, Guha and Bose-Rāy (*loc. cit.*). $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ breaks up on crystallisation from alcohol into $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ and $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ and with bases gives compounds both of the type $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot n\text{B}$ and $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot n\text{B}$ (*loc. cit.*). It appears improbable that the compound $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ has the constitution $[\text{Pt}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})_4] \cdot \text{PtCl}_6$ because $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ seldom gives a compound of the nature, $[\text{Pt B}_4] \text{PtCl}_6$ (B=Base), i.e., a compound of the empirical formula $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{B}$.

Hence, so far as the evidence goes, $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ appears to be a true compound of trivalent platinum possessing the constitution,

The co-ordination number is 4, and one chlorine atom is outside nucleus. This chlorine atom should behave differently from the other two, and should be ionisable and more labile and hence more reactive than the other two. It could not be proved directly that this chlorine atom outside the nucleus is ionisable as no ionising solvent could be found for the substance, in which its conductivity or molecular weight could be determined. That this chlorine atom is labile and hence reactive has however been amply proved by the action of bases on this compound.

Action of Bases on $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$.

The first action of the bases in most cases appears to reduce the compound, so that $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ is obtained and the base then enters the nucleus by substituting benzyl sulphide molecules, the substitution probably taking place in stages, though owing to inherent difficulty in arresting a reaction in the intermediate stages, partially substituted compounds could seldom be isolated. The base

may then further replace the chlorine atoms within the complex, so that the remaining two chlorine atoms come outside the nucleus and become ionisable. The following scheme illustrates the principle:—

The following compounds of the different types indicated above have been obtained:—

Type (I).—PtCl₂·2Bz₂S obtained by the action of dimethyl-aniline on PtCl₂·2 Bz₂S (the compound is the same as that obtained from chloroplatinic acid and benzylsulphide direct; *vide supra*).

Type (III).—PtCl₂·2PhNH₂.

Type (IV).—PtCl₂·3C₆H₁₁N.

Type (V).—PtCl₂·4 NH₃; PtCl₂·4BzNH₂; PtCl₂(en)₂; PtCl₂·4Py, where en=ethylene diamine; Py=pyridine.

The exceptions are Pt₂Cl₇·4Py and PtCl₂·Bz₂S·2 C₆H₁₁N.

Most of the above compounds are well known Werner compounds and have also been obtained by Rây, Guha and Bose-Rây and by Rây, Bose-Rây and Adhikari by the action of bases on PtCl₂·2 Et₂S, PtCl₂·2 Et₂S and PtCl₂·(C₂H₅)₂S, (*loc. cit*) and fully discussed.

That the compounds PtCl₂·4NH₃, PtCl₂·4Py, and PtCl₂(en)₂ are true compounds of the Type (V), possessing the constitution [Pt B₄]Cl₂, (B = NH₃, pyridine and $\frac{1}{2}$ ethylene diamine) has been shown by determining the ionisability of these compounds. All of them have both the chlorine atoms ionisable [*vide Experimental*; also Rây, Bose-Rây and Adhikari (*loc. cit*).]

The compound Pt₂Cl₇·4 Py (see above) would appear to be a molecular compound of PtCl₂·2 Py and PtCl₂·2Py, but as the substance was insoluble in common solvents it could not be broken up

into its constituents. RĀy, Bose-RĀy and Adhikari have also obtained this compound from $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot (\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$, (*loc. cit.*).

The Compound, $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2 \text{Bz}_2\text{S}$.

This compound previously obtained by Londahl from K_2PtCl_6 and benzyl sulphide (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1888, 38, 521) is a normal compound of bivalent platinum and possesses the constitution,

The action of bases on it has not yet been studied fully but it should evidently follow the scheme given for $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ as indicated by (II) to (V). The reaction with pyridine confirms this, as the compounds $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Py}$ (Type III) and $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{Py}$ (Type V) have been obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Chloroplatinic Acid and Benzyl Sulphide.

To an alcoholic solution (rectified spirit) of platonic chloride, benzyl sulphide was added, keeping the platonic chloride slightly in excess and heated under reflux for 4 to 5 hours. It was filtered hot. The filtrate on cooling, gave a crop of fine silky light yellow crystals which were filtered off and the mother-liquor was used over again to extract further quantities of the soluble portion from the insoluble residue. The insoluble portion was then heated under reflux twice with alcohol and filtered off. The silky yellow crystals that came down from the combined filtrates were washed with rectified spirit and then with ether to remove any excess of benzyl sulphide, and dried. The substance was greenish when crystallised from benzene, m. p. 159°. (Found: Pt, 27·96; Cl, 10·5; S, 9·23*. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ requires Pt, 28·1; Cl, 10·23; S, 9·22 per cent.).

The portion insoluble in alcohol was then washed with ether and recrystallised from benzene; m.p. 183°. (with decomp.) (Found: Pt, 26·27; Cl, 14·21, 15·14; S, 9·19. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ requires Pt, 26·7; Cl, 14·6; S, 8·77 per cent.).

* For estimation of sulphur, Carius' method followed by fusion with Na_2CO_3 and KNO_3 was employed. The nitric acid in the Carius' method was also supplemented by the addition of bromine. The reasons for these are given in *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1925, 2, 185 (footnote).

The Compound Pt₂Cl₆. 4Bz₂S.

When in the above reaction, platinum chloride was used in large excess, the first crop of the crystals that came down was reddish (instead of light yellow). In that case, the mother-liquor after the separation of the first crop of crystals was again treated with more benzyl sulphide and heated under reflux, when the two usual products PtCl₃.2Bz₂S and PtCl₃.2Bz₂S were obtained. The reddish crystals obtained as stated above were washed with alcohol and ether and dried; m.p. 158°. (Found: Pt, 27.66; Cl, 12.39. Pt₂Cl₆.4Bz₂S requires Pt, 27.4; Cl, 12.47 per cent.).

The substance, Pt₂Cl₆.4 Bz₂S when crystallised from alcohol broke up into PtCl₃.2 Bz₂S and PtCl₃.2 Bz₂S. PtCl₃.2 Bz₂S as usual remained insoluble, while PtCl₃.2 Bz₂S crystallised out from the hot filtrate as it cooled down. Both of them were washed and dried as before. The PtCl₃.2 Bz₂S and PtCl₃.2 Bz₂S thus obtained were identified by their melting points, solubility and colour. The percentage of platinum in each case was determined. (Found: Pt, 26.50. PtCl₃.2 Bz₂S requires Pt, 26.7 per cent. Found: Pt, 28.33. PtCl₃.2 Bz₂S requires Pt, 28.1 per cent.).

*Molecular Weight Determination of PtCl₃.2Bz₂S
in Naphthalene by the Cryoscopic Method.*

No. of observations.	Amount of solvent in grams.	Amount of PtCl ₃ .2 Bz ₂ S in grams.	Lowering of freezing point.	M.W. (found).	M.W. (calc.)
I.	34.3	1.0806	0.320°C	679	729
II.	37.5	2.0761	0.555°C	688	729

From the table we see that the molecular weight found by the cryoscopic method in naphthalene is about 680, whereas the molecular weight calculated, assuming PtCl₃.2 Bz₂S to be a simple molecule, is 729. The agreement is sufficient to conclude that PtCl₃.2Bz₂S consists of single molecules.

Action of Ammonia on PtCl₃.2Bz₂S.

PtCl₃.2 Bz₂S was covered up with a large excess of liquor ammonia in a flask, corked up and set aside and shaken daily for 3 weeks. It was then filtered and the filtrate evaporated to a very small bulk and diluted with alcohol. The first portions of the

precipitate were redissolved in a small amount of water and reprecipitated with alcohol. (This is necessary to remove any NH_4Cl which might be formed in the reaction). The first portion of the precipitate filtered off, washed with ether and dried, was brownish in colour and did not melt. (Found: Pt, 58·14; Cl, 21·07; N, 16·48. $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 4 \text{NH}_3$ requires Pt, 58·38; Cl, 21·26; N, 16·76 per cent.).

The Ionisability of $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{NH}_3$ (precipitation method).

The substance was dissolved in water and precipitated by AgNO_3 solution in the cold. No nitric acid was added, lest it should break up the complex. The result obtained is low, but sufficiently convincing to indicate that both the chlorine atoms are ionisable. (Found: Cl, 19·42. $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{NH}_3$ (assuming both the chlorine atoms to be ionisable) requires Cl, 21·26 per cent.).

Action of Benzylamine on $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$.

$\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2 \text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ was just covered with benzylamine and stirred with a rod. Great heat was evolved and hence during the reaction, which required 15 to 20 minutes, the mass was occasionally cooled by tap water. The mass was extracted with benzene, filtered and the filtrate allowed to evaporate. The residue left after the evaporation of benzene was brownish owing to enclosed tarry matters. It was washed several times with cold alcohol until an almost white substance was left. It was finally washed with hot alcohol and crystallised from chloroform; m. p. 195°. (Found: Pt, 28·42; Cl, 10·32; N, 8·43. $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{BzNH}_2$ requires Pt, 28·1; Cl, 10·23, N, 8·07 per cent.).

Action of Ethylene Diamine on $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2 \text{Bz}_2\text{S}$.

A 5% solution of ethylene diamine hydrate was added (slightly in excess) to $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2 \text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ in a hard glass test tube and heated on a water-bath until almost the whole went into solution (2 to 3 hours). It was allowed to cool, when benzyl sulphide separated out. This was filtered off and the filtrate evaporated to a small volume in a vacuum desiccator and precipitated with alcohol. The first crop of the precipitate was redissolved in a small amount of water and reprecipitated with alcohol. This is necessary to free the substance from the hydrochloride of the base that might be formed in the reaction. The substance was brownish, hygroscopic and did not melt up to 230°. (Found: Pt, 49·91; Cl, 17·56; N, 14·16. $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2$ requires Pt, 50·51; Cl, 18·39; N, 14·50 per cent.).

The Ionisability of PtCl₂(en)₂ (precipitation method).

The substance was dissolved in water and AgNO₃ solution added in the cold without adding nitric acid. The result obtained is slightly low. (Found: Cl, 17.60. PtCl₂(en)₂ (assuming both Cl atoms ionisable) requires Cl, 18.39 per cent.).

Action of Pyridine on PtCl₂ · 2 Bz₂S.

PtCl₂ · 2 Bz₂S was digested with an excess of pyridine on a water-bath for 6 to 8 hours, filtered hot and extracted 2 or 3 times with hot pyridine. The pyridine extracts were allowed to cool, when a white crystalline substance came down, which was filtered off and washed with ether several times. The substance was extremely soluble in water and was very hygroscopic. It turned yellow at 140° but did not melt. (Found: Pt, 33.09; Cl, 12.02; N, 8.7. PtCl₂ · 4 C₅H₅N requires Pt, 33.5; Cl, 12.19; N, 9.6 per cent.)

The insoluble portion was washed a few times more with hot pyridine, then with alcohol and water to remove the last traces of the white compound which was very soluble in water. It was then washed with alcohol, benzene and ether. The substance was insoluble in common organic solvents and did not melt. (Found: Pt, 40.48; Cl, 26.75; N, 5.48; C, 24.85; H, 2.18. Pt₂Cl₃ · 4 C₅H₅N requires Pt, 40.8; Cl, 26.03; N, 5.86; C, 25.09; H, 2.09 per cent.).

The Ionisability of PtCl₂ · 4Py.

(Found: Molecular conductivity at 1221 litres dilution (which may be practically taken to be infinite dilution)=276.

Hence, the substance is a ternary electrolyte (theoretical value for which is 260), that is, both the Cl atoms are ionisable.

Action of Aniline on PtCl₂ · 2 Bz₂S.

PtCl₂ · 2Bz₂S was digested with an excess of aniline on a water-bath for 3 to 4 hours. A reddish violet solution was obtained. This was filtered and the residue washed thoroughly with alcohol, until the filtrate was no longer coloured violet. It was then washed twice with water and again with alcohol and finally with ether and dried. The substance was dirty grey in colour and did not melt. (Found: Pt, 43.47; Cl, 16.01; N, 6.85. PtCl₂ · 2 PhNH₂ requires Pt, 43.14; Cl, 15.70; N, 6.2 per cent.).

The coloured filtrate contained mainly the oxidation products of aniline with only traces of platinum.

Action of Dimethylaniline on $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$.

$\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ was treated with a slight excess of dimethylaniline in a hard glass test tube and heated on a water-bath for 2 to 3 hours with occasional stirring with a rod. A deep violet solution was obtained. Alcohol was added and the solution filtered. The insoluble portion was washed several times with alcohol until the filtrate was no longer violet. The residue was then crystallised from hot benzene, washed with alcohol and ether and dried. The substance was obtained as greenish crystals, m.p. 159° . (Found: Pt, 28.13; Cl, 9.93; S, 8.97. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ requires Pt, 28.1; Cl, 10.23; S, 9.22 per cent.).

The substance $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ is the same as that obtained direct from chloroplatinic acid and benzylsulphide (*vide supra*).

The filtrate contained mainly oxidation products of dimethylaniline and was rejected.

Action of Piperidine on $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$.

(i) About 2 c.c. of piperidine were added to about 1 g. of $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ in a hard glass test tube and stirred with a rod. Great heat was evolved and the mass was occasionally cooled by tap water. The reaction was allowed to proceed for about 25 minutes. The semi-solid mass obtained was completely soluble in chloroform. The chloroform solution was allowed to evaporate to a small bulk and precipitated with ether. It was filtered and the precipitate freed from chloroform, washed with water, dried in a desiccator and dissolved in the smallest quantity of chloroform and reprecipitated with ether. The precipitate was filtered and dried. The substance was white with slight brownish tinge, m.p. 172° . (Found: Pt, 28.34; Cl, 14.91; N, 5.00. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_{11}\text{N} \cdot \text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ requires Pt, 28.42; Cl, 15.52; N, 4.08 per cent.).

(ii) Piperidine was added in excess to $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ in a hard glass test tube and stirred with a rod. Great heat was evolved as before. The reaction was allowed to take place for more than half an hour. The mass was dissolved in chloroform and precipitated with ether. The process was repeated as before, and the precipitate washed with water and ether and dried. The substance was white with a brownish tinge. (Found: Pt, 37.19; Cl, 13.97;

N, 8.16. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 3\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{N}$ requires Pt, 37.4; Cl, 13.62; N, 8.06 per cent.).

Action of Pyridine on $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$.

$\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ was digested with in excess of pyridine in a hard glass test tube on a water-bath for 5 to 6 hours, and filtered hot. The residue was extracted once or twice with hot pyridine. The combined pyridine extracts and the filtrate on evaporation gave white crystals, which were filtered off, washed with cold pyridine once and then thoroughly with chloroform, benzene and ether. The substance was white, had no m.p. but turned yellow above 140° . (Found: Pt, 33.07; Cl, 11.56. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires Pt, 33.50; Cl, 12.19 per cent.).

The substance is identical with that obtained from $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Bz}_2\text{S}$ and pyridine (*vide supra*).

The pyridine-insoluble portion was digested repeatedly with boiling chloroform and filtered hot until almost the whole went into solution. The filtrate, on spontaneous evaporation, gave fine yellow crystals, insoluble in water. These were collected, washed with chloroform (cold), ether, alcohol, water and again with alcohol and ether. (Found: Pt, 46.3; Cl, 17.01; N, 6.50. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires Pt, 46.0; Cl, 16.75; N, 6.60 per cent.).

$\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{Py}$ on being heated above 140° gave the yellow substance $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Py}$ which was extracted with boiling chloroform as above, dried and analysed. (Found: Pt, 46.2. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires Pt, 46.0 per cent.).

